

Synthesis of Nano-Structure Silicate Using Sol-Gel Technique

Semaa Basim Mohammed ✉

Department of Physics Sciences, College of Science, University of Baghdad, Iraq

Duea Shabib Shafi

Department of Physics Sciences, College of Science, Dhi-Qar University, Iraq

Zahraa Mohsen Ghyad

Department of Physics Sciences, College of Science, University of Basra, Iraq

Baraa Emad Odeh

Department of Physics Sciences, College of Science, University of Basra, Iraq

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Abstract:

Nano-structure SiO₂ was prepared in this work by use Sol-Gel method. By studying optical and structural properties of SiO₂, the absorption spectrum was determined in UV region, while nano-structure and morphology was investigated by XRD and AFM respectively. The particle size measured by use AFM Analysis which about (55.12 nm).

Keywords: nano-structure silicate, Sol-Gel method, SiO₂, structural properties

Introduction

The dynamic development of nanotechnology has been observed especially in the area of materials engineering. Excellent examples are various nanoparticles, where the current research is focused on their design, fabrication, characterization and applications. The properties and specific functions of nanoparticles may be controlled by their shape and size at the nanometer scale. There are several methods that have been put forward for synthesis of these materials, namely chemical vapor condensation, arc discharge, hydrogen plasma-metal reaction, and laser pyrolysis in the vapor phase, micro-emulsion, hydrothermal, sol-gel, etc (Tavakoli, Sohrabi, & Kargari, 2007; Research and market, 2020).

Silicon Dioxide

Silicon dioxide, also known as silica (from the Latin silex), is an oxide of silicon with the chemical formula SiO₂, most commonly found in nature as quartz and in various living organisms (Iler, 1979; Fernández, Lara, & Mitchell, 2015).

SiO₂ has been a subject of intensive research due to its outstanding physical and chemical characteristics. It exists in many crystalline forms, the better known being quartz, cristobalite, tridymite, stishovite, and coesite, but its best-known form is amorphous silicon dioxide. Therefore, amorphous silica continues as the focus of much fundamental research to understand its electronic structure, bonding characterization, defects, and optical properties. The inter-band optical properties having larger

transition strengths and index of refraction of crystalline quartz and amorphous SiO₂ vacuum in the ultraviolet UV region have been investigated using combined spectroscopic ellipsometry and UV spectroscopy (Suzuki, 2002; Lenza, & Vasconcelos, 2001; Henrich, & Cox, 1994). The growth of silicon dioxide is one of the most important processes in the fabrication of MOS transistor (Plummer, Deal, & Griffin, 2000).

The attributes of SiO which make it appealing for the semiconductor industry are; It has a high dielectric strength and a relatively wide band gap, making it an excellent insulator, it has high a temperature stability of up to 1600 C, making it a useful material for process and device integration (Plummer, Deal, & Griffin, 2000; Hollauer, 2007).

Table 1. Important Properties of SiO₂ (silicon dioxide)

Crystal structure	Amorphous
Atomic weight	60.08g/mole
Density (thermal, dry/wet)	2.27/2.18g/cm ³
Molecules	$2.3 \cdot 10^{22} / \text{cm}^3$
Specific heat	1.0J/g-K
Melting point	1700°C
Thermal expansion coefficient	$5.6 \cdot 10^{-7} / \text{K}$
Young's modulus	$6.6 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ N/m}^2$
Poisson's ratio	0.17
Thermal conductivity	1.1W/m-K - 1.4W/m-K
Relative dielectric constant	3.7 - 3.9
Dielectric strength	10 ⁷ V/cm
Energy bandgap	8.9eV

Source: El-Kareh, B. (1994)

Crystalline SiO₂ has more sharp features in the inter-band transition strength spectrum than amorphous SiO₂; the energy of the absorption edge for crystalline SiO₂ is about 1eV higher than that for amorphous SiO₂ (Valden, Lai, & Goodman, 1998; Millot, et al., 2005). the Si atom shows tetrahedral coordination, with four oxygen atoms surrounding a central Si atom. The most common example is seen in the quartzite polymorph.

SiO₂ has a number of distinct crystalline forms (polymorphs) in addition to amorphous forms. With the exception of stishovite and fibrous silica, all of the crystalline forms involve tetrahedral SiO₄ units linked together by shared vertices in different arrangements (Holleman, & Wiberg, 2001). The silicon dioxide has been synthesized by various techniques. There is significant interest in the synthesis of crystalline and uniform material, for the applications in microelectronics, optical, electrical and such various fields.

Figure 1. Crystal Structure of SiO₂

Sol-Gel Process

The methods of crystal growth can generally be grouped into two, thus; Vapour Phased Deposition which includes, Evaporation, Molecular Beam Epitaxy (MBE), Sputtering, Chemical Vapour Deposition(CVD) and Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) and Liquid Based Growth which includes Chemical Solution Deposition, Electrochemical Deposition, Chemical Bath Deposition(CBD), Successive Ionic Layer Adsorption and Reaction (SILAR), Langmuir- blodgett films and Self Assembled Monolayers (SAM) and Sol - gel method (Milton, et al., 2007; Jaeger, 2002).

Sol-gel process has been widely shown to be a very flexible route wet chemical techniques for the fabrication of a large variety of photonic materials in various configurations, such as

monoliths, coatings, fibers and films for optical device applications (Brinker, & Scherer, 1990).

The Sol-Gel Process Steps

the sol-gel method has five steps:

Hydrolysis

Metal alkoxides are popular precursors because they react readily with water. this reaction is called hydrolysis, because a hydroxyl ion become attached to metal, as the following reaction:

metal alkoxide metal hydroxide

Condensation

Condensation liberates a small molecule, such as water or alcohol. this type of reaction can continue to build and larger silicon-containing molecules by process of polymerization, as the following reaction:

Aging

The processes of change during aging after gelation are categorized as polymerization, coarsening, and phase transformation.

polymerization is the increase in connectivity of the network produced by condensation reactions, such as

Drying

The process of drying of a porous material be divided into several stages. At first the body shrinks by an amount equal to the volume of

liquid that evaporates, and the liquid -vapor interface remains at the exterior surface of the body. and second stage begins when the body becomes too stiff to shrink and the liquid recedes into the interior, leaving air-filled pore *near the surface*.

Calcination

After dried the samples we were putted it in Furnace at 300C.

Application of SiO₂:

Uses of silica include:

- production of window glass, drinking glasses and beverage bottle.
- optical fibers for telecommunications.
- analytical instruments - UV spectrophotometer cells, military fire control devices, reticle substrates, interferometer plates.
- a primary raw material for many whiteware ceramics such as earthenware, stoneware and porcelain, as well as industrial Portland cement.
- an additive in the production of foods, pharmaceuticals and health supplements, where it is used primarily as a smoothing agent (think Peanut Butter) and as a flow agent in powdered products and in pill manufacture.

Coating Method

A coating is a covering that is applied to the surface of an object, usually referred to as the substrate. The purpose of applying the coating may be decorative, functional, or both. The coating itself may be an all-over coating, completely covering the substrate, or it may only cover parts of the substrate. An example of all of these types of coating is a product label on many drinks' bottles- one side has an all-over functional coating (the adhesive) and the other side has one or more decorative coatings in an appropriate pattern (the printing) to form the words and images.

Coating Types

Dip-coating: - is an industrial coating process which is used, for example, to manufacture bulk

products such as coated fabrics and condoms and specialized coatings for example in the biomedical field. Dip coating is also commonly used in academic research, where many chemical and nanomaterial engineering research projects use the dip coating technique to create thin-film coating (Scriven, 2011).

Spin coating: this process has been widely used in the manufacture of integrated circuits optical mirrors, color television screens and magnetic disk for data storage.

Centrifugal force drives the liquid radial outward. The viscous force and surface tension causes a thin residual film to be retained on the flat substrate. The film thins by the combination of outward fluid flow and evaporation. spin coating can be broken down into several key stages: fluid dispense, spin-up, stable fluid out flow, and finally evaporation dominated drying (Sahu, Parija, & Panigrahi, 2009).

Thermal spray coating: thermal spraying techniques are coating processes in which melted (or heated) materials are sprayed onto a surface. The "feedstock" (coating precursor) is heated by electrical (plasma or arc) or chemical means (combustion flame).

Thermal spraying can provide thick coatings (approx. thickness range is 20 microns to several mm, depending on the process and feedstock), over a large area at high deposition rate as compared to other coating processes such as electroplating, physical and chemical vapor deposition. Coating materials available for thermal spraying include metals, alloys, ceramics, plastics and composites. They are fed in powder or wire form, heated to a molten or semi-molten state and accelerated towards substrates in the form of micrometer-size particles. Combustion or electrical arc discharge is usually used as the source of energy for thermal spraying. Resulting coatings are made by the accumulation of numerous sprayed particles. The surface may not heat up significantly, allowing the coating of flammable substances (Kuroda, et al., 2008).

Sputtering-coating: sputtering is a process whereby particles are ejected from a solid target material due to bombardment of the target by

energetic particles (Tavakoli, Sohrabi, & Kargari, 2007), particularly gas ions in a laboratory. It only happens when the kinetic energy of the incoming particles is much higher than conventional thermal energies ($\gg 1$ eV). This process can lead, during prolonged ion or plasma bombardment of a material, to significant erosion of materials, and can thus be harmful. On the other hand, it is commonly used for thin-film deposition, etching and analytical techniques. Sputtering is done either using DC voltage (DC sputtering) or using AC voltage (RF sputtering). In DC sputtering, voltage is set from 3-5 kV and in RF sputtering, power supply is set at 14 MHz. Due to the application of an alternating current, the ions inside the plasma oscillate resulting in an increases in the levels of plasma.

Literature Survey

The literature survey in the current research study can be summarized in three parts as follows:

Stober et al. in 1968 reported a pioneering method for the synthesis of spherical and monodispersed silicon dioxide nanoparticles from aqueous alcohol solutions of silicon alkoxides.

Through this method, different sizes of silicon dioxide nanoparticles were prepared ranging from 50 nm to 1 μ m with a narrow size distribution. The sizes of particles were depended on the type of silicon alkoxide and alcohol (Rao et al. , 2005). This method consisted of hydrolysis of tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) using ammonia as catalyst an ethanol as solvent. Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), water, pentanol, and ammonia were used as precursors.

Stucky et al. (1994) have reported that an acid synthesis route of mesoporous silica ($\text{pH} < 2.0$) could usually lead to many topological constructions. Silicon dioxide can be synthesized in either the alkaline route or the acid route both using amphiphiles as templates. In the acid route, the precursor of silicon dioxide could be silicon alkoxides. The acid catalysis speeds up the hydrolysis versus the condensation rate and

promotes mostly condensation at the ends of silicon dioxide polymers to form linear silicate ions. The alkaline catalysis favors both hydrolysis and condensation. Thus, the alkaline route leads to a highly condensed and compact structure, and the acid route leads to a more fuzzy and soft network (Liden et al., 2001).

Ming-Zhi et al. (2004) prepared nanoparticles silicon dioxide films from hydrolysis of tetraethyl orthosilicate, TEOS with catalyzed by R 4 NOH in water medium using the sol gel process. Silicon dioxide thin films were formed after being annealed at high temperature. Larry and Jon (1990) reported that silicon dioxide gel was heated at elevated temperature which is called densification in sol-gel process to reduce pores and to increase surface of gel.

Methods

SiO₂ Fabrication

We prepared SiO₂ liquid by sol-gel process and applied it several measurements such as, optical properties by (uv-visible spectroscopy), and by Structural properties (x-ray diffraction, atomic force microscopy).

SiO₂ Preparation

(SiO₂) sol was prepared using the following materials:

- Isopropanol alcohol, (C₃H₈O), from Merck.
- Deionized water.

Tetraethylorthosilicate(TEOS),[Si(OC₂H₅)₄],Purity98%,from sigma-Aldrich.

The process utilized according to the following procedure:

Isopropanol Alcohol of (15.4 ml) was mixed with (1 ml) of deionized water. Meanwhile, HNO₃ of (0.8 ml) was added drop wise at (0 °C) (4.4 ml) of (TEOS) which then mixed with (15.6 ml) of Isopropanol Alcohol. The resultant sol was stirred for 2 hours, yielding a transparent sol.

Figure 2. Image of Prepared SiO₂

Figure 3. Experimental Part

Dip-coating of SiO₂

Among the various wet chemical thin film deposition methods dip coating represents the oldest commercially applied coating process. The first patent based on this process was issued to Jenaer Glaswerk Schott & Gen. in 1939 for sol-gel derived silica films. Nowadays sol-gel or more general CSD derived coatings are being studied for a manifold range of applications such as ferroelectrics, dielectrics, sensors and

actuators, membranes, superconducting layers, protective coatings, passivation layers, etc. (see Part V of this book). Basically the process may be separated into three important technical stages:

1. Immersion & dwell time: The substrate is immersed into the precursor solution at a constant speed followed by a certain dwell time in order to leave sufficient interaction time of the substrate with the coating solution for complete wetting.
2. Deposition & Drainage: By pulling the substrate upward at a constant speed a thin layer of precursor solution is entrained, i.e. film deposition. Excess liquid will drain from the surface.
3. Evaporation: The solvent evaporates from the fluid, forming the as-deposited thin film, which can be promoted by heated drying. Subsequently the coating may be subjected to further heat treatment in order to burn out residual organics and induce crystallization of the functional oxides (Brinker, 2013).

Figure 4. Image of Dip-Coating Method

The Devices Used for Measurement

Study of XRD of SiO_2 Structures

X-ray scattering techniques are a family of non-destructive analytical techniques which reveal information about the crystal structure, chemical composition, and physical properties of materials and thin films. These techniques are based on observing the scattered intensity of an

X-ray beam hitting a sample as a function of incident and scattered angle, polarization, and wavelength or energy.

Note that X-ray diffraction is now often considered a sub-set of X-ray scattering, where the scattering is elastic and the scattering object is crystalline, so that the resulting pattern contains sharp spots analyzed by X-ray crystallography. However, both scattering and diffraction are related general phenomena and the distinction has not always existed. Thus Guinier's classic text from 1963 is titled "X-ray diffraction in Crystals, Imperfect Crystals and Amorphous Bodies" so 'diffraction' was clearly not restricted to crystals at that time (Guinier, 1963).

Figure 5. Image of X-ray Diffraction Device

Atomic Force Microscopy

The Atomic Force Microscope is a kind of scanning probe microscope in which a topographical image of the SiO_2 surface can be achieved based on the interactions between a tip and a sample surface. The atomic force microscope was invented by Gerd Binnig et al. in 1986 at IBM Zurich based on the STM (Scanning Tunneling Microscope) already presented in 1981. While the latter depends on the conductive samples, the AFM allows also the use of non-conductive samples. In 1987, the inventors were awarded the Nobel Prize in

Physics for the achievements.

A typical AFM consists of a cantilever with a small tip (probe) at the free end, a laser, a 4-quadrant photodiode and a scanner.

UV-Vis Absorption

The UV-Visible absorption spectra of SiO₂ synthesized via sol-gel route dried at 110°C and calcined at 300°C. The band gap energies (E_g) of samples were determined by the

$$E_g = h c \lambda \quad (1)$$

Where, E_g is the band gap (eV), h is the Planck's constant (4.135 x 10⁻⁶ eV), c is the velocity of light (3 x 10⁸ ms⁻¹), and λ wavelength of the absorption edge in the spectrum.

Figure 6. Image of UV-Vis Spectrophotometer

Results and Discussion

X-Ray Diffraction

X-ray diffraction is a powerful non-destructive method for material characterization, by which

the crystal structure, orientation and grain size can be determined. The characterization is usually carried out with a typical X-ray wavelength that is comparable to the interatomic distance in a crystal in figure 7.

sharp peaks in the corresponding directions. They are called Bragg peaks. The Bragg peak can be found by varying the angle 2θ of the detector.

$$2d \sin \theta = m \lambda \quad (2)$$

Where m is integer

we can find the size of the sub-micrometer particles or crystallites by using Debye-Scherrer equation as illustrated below:

$$D = K \lambda / \beta \cos \theta \quad (3)$$

where, D is the average crystallite size, K is a constant depend on the crystallite shape (0.9), λ is the X-ray wavelength (in this case, λ = 1.5418), β is the full width at half maxima (FWHM), and θ is the Bragg's angle. Using the above equation we can determine the size of the particles. On comparing our obtained XRD spectrum from the JCPDS Card #850335 for SiO₂, we can assure that the material formed is SiO₂ (Quartz) nanoparticles, as the peaks reveal the formation of particles having dimensions in nm range and the reflection from (100), (110), (102), (111), (200) and (201) planes, at 2θ values 20.861°, 36.550°, 39.470°, 40.296°, 42.457°, and 45.800°, for the sample synthesized via sol-gel route. From the XRD pattern, it is clear that the material formed is having hexagonal crystal structure and is primitive lattice with lattice parameters a=b=4.913 Å and c=5.405 Å.

Figure 7. X-Ray Pattern for the Sample (SiO₂)

UV-VIS Absorption of SiO₂

The Absorbance of SiO₂ in the spectral range of (300–800) nm used in this work, Then Tauc law was used to obtain the energy gap of (SiO₂) sample:

$$(\alpha h\nu) = \mathcal{A}(h\nu - E_b)^n \quad (4)$$

Where:

- α Titania absorption coefficient
- $h\nu$ Energy of the incident photons
- \mathcal{A} Corresponding absorption constant
- E_b Absorption band gap energy

Figure 8. a-The absorption spectra of SiO₂; b- The energy gab of SiO₂

The absorption curve and the energy gap is shown in figure 9.

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)

In order to evaluate the surface roughness and morphologies of the optimized samples for each group, atomic force microscopy technique has been used. Figures (9 a, b) show the (2D) and

(3D) images of the sample (SiO_2). The images indicate that; the formations of fine agglomerations consist of compact nanoparticles with non-uniform grain size. Figure (9c) shows the histogram of the same sample. The Grain size calculated from this figure which was about (55.12 nm).

a

b

c

Figure 9. AFM Images for the Sample (SiO_2)
a- 2D Image; b-3D Image; c- Histogram

Conclusion

1. Sol-Gel method can be used to get SiO₂ particles in nano scale.
2. Amorphous phase of SiO₂ is the winner at 300°C.
3. The images of AFM indicate that the formations of fine agglomerations consist of compact nanoparticles with non-uniform grain size.

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